

Propolis mitigates rifampicin/isoniazid induced lipid-redox and metabolic profile in an experimental animal model

El propóleo mitiga el perfil metabólico y lípido-redox inducido por rifampicina/isoniazida en un modelo animal experimental

Ahmed Abdulsallam, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8462-0359>, Alkhansaa Teaching hospital, Mosul, Iraq.

Imad A. Thanoon*, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5783-6878>, College of Medicine, University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq. imadpharma@yahoo.com

Rwqaya S. Dawood, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0602-4794>, College of Medicine, University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq

Abdulrahman I. Abduljabbar, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2584-7174>, Graduated Physician, University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq

*Correspondence author: Ahmed Abdulsallam ahmed.hmp22@student.uomosul.edu.iq

Received: 04/26/2021 Accepted: 07/15/2022 Published: 07/25/2022 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7357850>

Abstract

Adverse drug reactions are the most common cause of drug withdrawal in chronic treatment settings. Tuberculosis (TB) has been considered a recurrent and relapsing disease that needs long-term therapy. Most patients suffer from the adverse effects of TB therapy. Hence, various remedies were used to tackle these adverse effects including antioxidant vitamins, herbal remedies, and others. The present intervention study aims to investigate the role of propolis in protecting the animal model against oxidant/antioxidant induced by TB therapy together with the propolis role in modulation of metabolic profile as part of lipid peroxidation context. To do so, serum was collected from rats exposed to rifampicin/isoniazid with or without propolis therapy alongside the control placebo group for comparison. The results have shown a significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction of malondialdehyde and significant ($p < 0.05$) elevation of total antioxidant status. Lipid profile positively improved indicated by significantly reduced total cholesterol, triglyceride, and elevated high-density lipoprotein. In conclusion, our study confirmed that propolis provides protection against redox and metabolic derangement induced by rifampicin/isoniazid medications which are in current TB therapy, therefore, we do advise the use of propolis as an adjunct therapy for patients on such medications.

Keywords: isoniazid, rifampicin, propolis, FBS, TAS, MDA, and lipid.

Resumen

Las reacciones adversas a medicamentos son la causa más común de abstinencia de medicamentos en entornos de tratamiento crónico. La tuberculosis (TB) se ha considerado una enfermedad recurrente y con recaídas que necesita una terapia a largo plazo. La mayoría de los pacientes sufren los efectos adversos del tratamiento de la TB. Por lo tanto, se utilizaron varios remedios para abordar estos efectos adversos, incluidas las vitaminas antioxidantes, los remedios a base de hierbas y otros. El presente estudio de intervención tiene como objetivo investigar el papel del propóleo en la protección del modelo animal contra el oxidante/antioxidante inducido por la terapia de TB junto con el papel del propóleo en la modulación del perfil metabólico como parte del contexto de la peroxidación lipídica. Para hacerlo, se recolectó suero de ratas expuestas a rifampicina/isoniazida con o sin terapia de propóleos junto con el grupo de control con placebo para comparar. Los resultados han mostrado una reducción significativa ($p < 0,05$) de malondialdehído y una elevación significativa ($p < 0,05$) del estado antioxidante total. Perfil de lípidos mejorado positivamente indicado por colesterol total significativamente reducido, triglicéridos y lipoproteínas de alta densidad elevadas. En conclusión, nuestro estudio confirmó que el propóleos brinda protección contra el trastorno redox y metabólico inducido por los medicamentos de rifampicina/isoniazida que se encuentran en la terapia actual contra la TB; por lo tanto, recomendamos el uso de propóleos como terapia adjunta para los pacientes que toman dichos medicamentos.

Palabras clave: isoniazida, rifampicina, propóleo, FBS, TAS, MDA y lípido.

Introduction

In the Middle Ages and classic times, many bee products have been used for various purposes. These products include propolis, bee wax, royal jelly, honey, and bee pollen is being used for beauty purposes in ancient China. These products are also been used as effective medicines in today's era¹⁻⁵. The use of such products is also growing in treating cancers, neurogenerative diseases, cardiovascular diseases, and gastrointestinal tract-related disorders. Treatment of wounds and burns can also be performed effectively using bee-related beneficial products⁶⁻¹⁰. Adverse impacts of oxidative stress regarding the aetiology of various diseases could also be encountered by the use of bee products that acts as an effective source of natural anti-oxidants.

Mainly, the anti-oxidant capacity of bee products is accountable to substances having phenolic characters that have the power to rummage for free radicals¹¹⁻¹⁴. Phenolic acids and flavonoids are the two main groups of such compounds¹⁵. Neoflavanoids, isoflavones, chalcones, anthocyanins, flavanols, as well as flavanones, are the plant-based derivatives of flavonoids and the best of the subgroups related to flavonoids are those consisting of benzo-gamma pyrone skeleton. Flavanoids are mainly responsible for playing their role in aglycones linked by a "glycosidic bond" with a carbohydrate group. Flavonoids are usually present themselves in the form of glycosides¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Phenol groups are also present in flavonoids that pass on them with the anti-radical activity because the radicals established during metabolic processing¹⁶. The present study tested the function of propolis in attenuating the oxidative stress induced by rifampicin and/or isoniazid.

Materials and Methods

To implement the objectives of the present study, an experimental rat model was used by exposing the rodent to rifampicin and/or isoniazid with the restoration of pro-oxidant status by propolis therapy. A total of 64 rats were used (eight in each group); divided into eight groups in total. Each group were given the specific medication and dose on daily basis (see Table 1) [negative control group received normal saline, the positive control group received propolis only, rifampicin group and isoniazid group received rifampicin or isoniazid or a combination of them with/without propolis]. The animals were kept in standard conditions adopted by "animal house in the College of Veterinary Medicine/University of Mosul".

Table 1. Origin and supplier's details of used medication in the present study.

Medications	Trade Name	Suppliers	Dose
Isoniazid	INH	KOCAK FARMA	50mg/Kg/day
Rifampicin	Sinerdol	Antibiotice	100mg/Kg/day
Propolis	Propolis	NOW	200mg/Kg/day

A serum sample is withdrawn from an individual rat before starting any medication administration; a second serum sample has been collected after 8 weeks of continuous drug administration. A schematic illustration describing workflow is provided below (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Workflow diagram.

The biochemical tests were conducted using kits specified in Table 2 below. The measurement of the concentration of glucose, total cholesterol, and triglycerides was conducted according to manufacturer instruction provided in the kit leaflets which through a few steps results in the conversion of the colorless molecules into quinone imine which is a chromogenic compound to be quantified at wavelength 500nm. Cholesterol in HDL molecules was quantified in the same manner after an initial step of their precipitation via phosphotungstic acid and magnesium chloride. Malondialdehyde (MDA) detection based on "ELISA technique", sampled were applied into primed surface plastic with "capture antibody" and after subsequent steps of washing and exposure to detection antibody followed by "enzymatic reaction" using avidin conjugated to "horseradish peroxidase" to be ended by addition of "Tetramethylbenzidine substrate", the analysis ended through exposure to stop solution. Total antioxidant status (TAS) measurement based on colorimetric test using kit mentioned in table 2; the test based on ferrous-ferri conversion followed by the formation of equimolar concentration of colored compound following their reaction with phenanthroline substance.

Table 2. Kits and suppliers were used in the present study.

Medications	Catalogue No.	Suppliers	Origin
FBS	AT-80009	Biolabo	France
TC	AT-80106	Biolabo	France
TG	AT-80019	Biolabo	France
HDL	AT-86516	Biolabo	France
TAS	E-BC-K136-S	Elabscience	USA
MDA	E-EL-0060	Elabscience	USA

Results

To identify the role of propolis in the modulation of glycemic control; glucose level and weight were measured in all studied groups and the results were plotted against propolis-free groups. Regarding FBS (mg/dl) levels; there were non-significant ($p < 0.05$) differences between all groups before initiation of the therapy whether in propolis-treated or propolis-free therapy; the levels in all groups are close to the negative control group (102 ± 10.7); except the propolis-treated positive control group has shown significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction (FBS = 94.8 ± 5.2) compared to before starting the propolis therapy (Figure 2A). The weight has been measured as an additional parameter reflecting the health status of the experimental animals. The weight (g) results have shown non-significant ($p < 0.05$) differences between all groups before initiation of the therapy whether in propolis-treated or propolis-free therapy; the levels in all groups are close to the control group (212.9 ± 28.1). On the other hand, all propolis-treated groups have shown significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher weight gain compared to parallel propolis-free groups and the level were highest in the propolis-treated positive control group (327.9 ± 31.1) (Figure 2B).

Figure 2. Propolis induced weight gain in the studied groups with no effects on FBS. Rat weight (g) and FBS (mg/dl) were measured before and after propolis therapy in all studied groups. Data expressed as mean $\pm$ SD. $+p < 0.05$ significantly higher in propolis group as a compared propolis-free group. FBS=fasting blood sugar, C=control, p=propolis, INH=isoniazid, R=rifampicin.

To identify the role of propolis in the modulation of redox status; TAS and MDA concentrations were measured in all studied groups and the results were plotted against propolis-free groups. Regarding TAS (mM) levels; there were no significant differences between all groups before initiation of the therapy whether in propolis-treated or propolis-free therapy; the levels in all groups are close to the negative control group (1.45 ± 0.13) (Figure 3A). The positive control propolis-treated group showed significantly higher TAS levels compared to the control negative propolis free group. On the other hand, TAS levels were significantly reduced in propolis-free experimental animals following their exposure to either INH or rifampicin or a combination of them reaching a level down to (0.68 ± 0.16). However, TAS levels were significantly elevated in propolis-treated experimental animals following their exposure to either INH or rifampicin or a combination of them reaching a level up to (1.74 ± 0.16) (Figure 3A).

Regarding MDA ($\mu\text{mol/L}$) levels; there were no significant differences between all groups before initiation of the therapy whether in propolis-treated or propolis-free therapy; the levels in all groups are close to the negative control group (12.86 ± 1.18) (Figure 3B). The positive control propolis-treated group showed a significantly lower MDA level compared to the control negative propolis-free group. On the other hand, MDA levels were significantly elevated in propolis-free experimental animals following their exposure to either INH or rifampicin or a combination of them reaching a level up to (27.56 ± 1.07). However, MDA levels were significantly reduced in propolis-treated experimental animals following their exposure to either INH or rifampicin or a combination of them reaching a level down to (15.01 ± 1.53) (Figure 3B).

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 3. Propolis improved redox status in all studied groups. Serum TAS and MDA were measured before and after propolis therapy in all studied groups. Data expressed as mean $\pm$ SD. +p<0.05 significantly higher in propolis group as a compared propolis-free group. -p<0.05 significantly higher in the propolis-free group as compared to the propolis-treated group. C=control, P=propolis, INH=isoniazid, R=rifampicin. TAS=total antioxidant status, MDA= malondialdehyde.

Regarding TG, TC, and LDL (mg/dl) levels; there were no significant differences (p<0.05) between all groups before initiation of the therapy whether in propolis-treated or propolis-free therapy; the levels in all groups are close to the negative control group (TG =119.6 $\pm$ 5.4, TC=121 $\pm$ 7.9, and LDL=47.55 $\pm$ 6.62) (Figure 4A, B, D). The positive control propolis-treated group showed significantly lower TG, TC, and LDL levels compared to the control negative propolis-free group. On the other hand, TG, TC, and LDL levels were significantly elevated in propolis-free experimental animals following their exposure to either INH or rifampicin or a combination of them reaching to a level up to (TG = 134.8 $\pm$ 8.4, TC= 132.7 $\pm$ 4.4, and LDL= 66.98 $\pm$ 4.16). However, TG, TC, and LDL levels were significantly reduced in propolis-treated experimental animals following their exposure to either INH or rifampicin or a combination of them reaching to a level down to (TG = 116.9 $\pm$ 7, TC= 116.5 $\pm$ 7.4, and LDL= 50.21 $\pm$ 6.83) (Figure 4A, B, D).

Regarding HDL (mg/dl) levels; there were no significant differences (p<0.05) between all groups before initiation of the therapy whether in propolis-treated or propolis-free therapy; the levels in all groups are close to the negative control group (49.51 $\pm$ 1.98) (Figure 4C). Positive control propolis-treated group showed non-significantly HDL level compared to control negative propolis free group. On the other hand, HDL levels were significantly reduced in propolis-free experimental animals following their exposure to either INH or rifampicin or a combination of them reaching a level down to (38.73 $\pm$ 1.3). However, TAS levels were significantly elevated in propolis-treated experimental animals following their exposure to either INH or rifampicin or a combination of them reaching a level up to (42.69 $\pm$ 3.07) (Figure 4C).

Figure 4. Propolis improved lipid profile in all studied groups. Serum TC, TG, HDL, and LDL were measured before and after propolis therapy in all studied groups. Data expressed as mean $\pm$ SD. +p<0.05 significantly higher in propolis group as a compared propolis-free group. -p<0.05 significantly higher in the propolis-free group as compared to the propolis-treated group. C=control, p=propolis, INH=isoniazid, R=rifampicin. TC=total cholesterol, TG=triglycerides, HDL=high density lipoprotein, and LDL=low density lipoprotein

Figure 4

Discussion

Propolis has significantly inhibited the oxidative damage induced by vitiated insult (rifampicin and isoniazid). These deleterious action of propolis has been confirmed through the measuring of TAS and MDA. Rifampicin and isoniazid; in combination or alone, have significantly induced oxidative stress status revealed by significant elevation of MDA and reduction of TAS. When these insults were applied in combination with propolis the defective oxidation disappeared indicated by a significant elevation of TAS and a significant reduction in MDA. Correspondingly, these actions were positively reflected on the lipid profile i.e. propolis has significantly interfered with the elevated lipid profile induced by rifampicin or isoniazid on a combination of them¹⁷.

The antioxidant properties of propolis have been confirmed in different *in vitro* laboratory studies. Different methods have been used in understanding the capacities and properties of propolis including DPPH, ABTS+, FRAP, and ORAC^{3,18-25}. The impacts of the oral administration of propolis solution, on the oxidative status and lipid profile in a human population in Chile has been evaluated by Mujica et al.²⁶. A decline in the quantity of thiobarbituric acid reactive substances and gain in decreased glutathione (GSH) level compared to the baseline have been examined in propolis supplementation.

Following propolis supplementation, again in the HDL concentration compared to the initial values was examined and evaluated. Positive impacts on oxidative status and the improvement of HDL of propolis supplementation have been observed by the researchers. It is also observed to be proven beneficial in the reduction in the risk of cardiovascular problems. Positive antioxidant effects obtained on antioxidant enzymes, and a lipid peroxidation marker—malondialdehyde (MDA), using 30-day supplementation with the powdered propolis extract that is available in the market (a total daily dose of flavonoids was 48.75 mg) in healthy individuals was examined by Jasprica et al.²⁷.

After 15 days of the propolis treatment process, a 23.2% decline in MDA level was examined. A 20.9% gain in SOD activity after 30 days of propolis treatment was observed. However, MDA concentration was observed as same as that of baseline value at the end of the treatment process, surprisingly. As such no negative or positive impact on any of the studied parameters in women ($n = 15$) were observed as a result of the propolis treatment. The impacts of propolis were observed both time and gender-dependent in conclusion by the authors as the result of their studies. A possibility of the existence of only the transitory effect of propolis ingestion on lipid peroxidation has been suggested by the authors²⁶⁻³⁰.

The impact of propolis on lipid profile has been confirmed *in vitro* cell culture by Fang et al., using “human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs)”. The study confirmed that oxidized LDL, MDA, reactive oxygen species generation, and nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide oxidase activation were reduced²⁸. An action that has been further confirmed in a study conducted by Tian et al.²⁹, who has reported propolis provided protection against macrophage apoptosis induced by ox-LDL. Glucose-induced oxidative vascular damage has been attenuated in rat aorta using a propolis-based *in vitro* model³⁰⁻³³.

The positive effects of propolis in reducing lipid and oxidative stress were comparable to pharmacological interventions of statins and antioxidant vitamins or micronutrients in current use³⁴⁻³⁹. The exact molecular mechanism is incompletely understood. However, in the study conducted by Zhao et al.³⁷ on patients with “type 2 diabetes mellitus” (T2DM), a study examines the impacts of Brazilian green propolis supplementation regarding antioxidant status. A gain in serum levels of GSH and total polyphenols and decrease in serum carbonyls (protein oxidation markers) with that of lactate dehydrogenase activity was found to be linked by propolis administration. Furthermore, a decreased TNF- α serum level and importantly in-

creased IL-1 β and IL-6 sera levels were found in the Brazilian green propolis group. Hence, "serum glucose, glycosylated hemoglobin, insulin, aldose reductase, and adiponectin" levels were not found to be affected by propolis treatment. Only the oxidative stress in "type 2 diabetic patients" is affected by the propolis treatment according to the results of the above-mentioned studies. But there is no such effect was observed related to the parameters of diabetes.

Conclusion

In the present study, we demonstrated a model of oxidative stress using commonly indicated TB-therapy drugs (rifampicin and isoniazid), we did find that TB therapy impaired oxidative stress and lipid profile in a rat model and propolis protected against the deleterious damage of TB therapy whether as a monotherapy or in combination. Our recommendation is to advise TB patients to conjoin their therapy with propolis.

Acknowledgment

The authors thank the College of Medicine and College of Veterinary Medicine/University of Mosul for the facilities provided to accomplish this work.

Funding: Self-Funded

Adherence to Ethical Standards: The study was approved by the Medical Research Ethics Committee in the university of Mosul, the study approval number and date UOM/COM/MREC/2020-2021 (32) on 07/04/2021.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that no conflict of interest exists for this research

References

1. Yıldız O, Can Z, Saral Ö, Yuluğ E, Öztürk F, Aliyazıcıoğlu R, Canpolat S, Kolaylı S. Hepatoprotective potential of chestnut bee pollen on carbon tetrachloride-induced hepatic damages in rats. Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine. 2013;2013. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/461478>
2. Denisow B, Denisow-Pietrzyk M. Biological and therapeutic properties of bee pollen: a review. Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture. 2016 Oct;96(13):4303-9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.7729>
3. Sun C, Wu Z, Wang Z, Zhang H. Effect of ethanol/water solvents on phenolic profiles and antioxidant properties of Beijing propolis extracts. Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine. 2015 Jul;2015. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/595393>
4. Kumari S, Naik P, Vishma BL, Salian SR, Devkar RA, Khan S, Mutalik S, Kalthur G, Adiga SK. Mitigating effect of Indian propolis against mitomycin C induced bone marrow toxicity. Cytotechnology. 2016 Oct;68(5):1789-800. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10616-015-9931-4>
5. Alyane M, Keba LB, Boussenane HN, Rouibah H, Lahouel M. Cardioprotective effects and mechanism of action of polyphenols extracted from propolis against doxorubicin toxicity. Pakistan Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences. 2008 Jul 1;21(3).
6. Jin X, Liu Q, Jia L, Li M, Wang X. Pinocebrin attenuates 6-OHDA-induced neuronal cell death through Nrf2/ARE pathway in SH-SY5Y cells. Cellular and molecular neurobiology. 2015 Apr;35(3):323-33. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10571-014-0128-8>
7. Silva RB, Santos NA, Martins NM, Ferreira DA, Barbosa Jr F, Souza VO, Kinoshita A, Baffa O, Del-Bel E, Santos AC. Caffeic acid phenethyl ester protects against the dopaminergic neuronal loss induced by 6-hydroxydopamine in rats. Neuroscience. 2013 Mar 13;233:86-94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2012.12.041>
8. Izuta H, Shimazawa M, Tsuruma K, Araki Y, Mishima S, Hara H. Bee products prevent VEGF-induced angiogenesis in human umbilical vein endothelial cells. BMC complementary and alternative medicine. 2009 Dec;9(1):1-0. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-9-45>
9. Bazmandegan G, Boroushaki MT, Shamsizadeh A, Ayoobi F, Hakimizadeh E, Allahtavakoli M. Brown propolis attenuates cerebral ischemia-induced oxidative damage via affecting antioxidant enzyme system in mice. Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy. 2017 Jan 1;85:503-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2016.11.057>
10. Baltas N, Karaoglu SA, Tarakci C, Kolaylı S. Effect of propolis in gastric disorders: inhibition studies on the growth of Helicobacter pylori and production of its urease. Journal of enzyme inhibition and medicinal chemistry. 2016 Nov 2;31(sup2):46-50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14756366.2016.1186023>
11. LeBlanc BW, Davis OK, Boue S, DeLucca A, Deeby T. Antioxidant activity of Sonoran Desert bee pollen. Food chemistry. 2009 Aug 15;115(4):1299-305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2009.01.055>
12. Ferreira D, Rocha HC, Kreutz LC, Loro VL, Marqueze A, Koakoski G, Santos da Rosa JG, Gusso D, Oliveira TA, de Abreu MS, Barcellos LJ. Bee products prevent agrichemical-induced oxidative damage in fish. PLoS one. 2013 Oct 3;8(10):e74499. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0074499>
13. Kim SB, Jo YH, Liu Q, Ahn JH, Hong IP, Han SM, Hwang BY, Lee MK. Optimization of extraction condition of bee pollen using response surface methodology: correlation between anti-melanogenesis, antioxidant activity, and phenolic content. Molecules. 2015 Nov;20(11):19764-74. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules201119656>
14. de Florio Almeida J, dos Reis AS, Heldt LF, Pereira D, Bianchin M, de Moura C, Plata-Oviedo MV, Haminiuk CW, Ribeiro IS, da Luz CF, Carpes ST. Lyophilized bee pollen extract: A natural antioxidant source to prevent lipid oxidation in refrigerated sausages. LWT-Food Science and Technology. 2017 Mar 1;76:299-305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2016.06.017>
15. Rzepecka-Stojko A, Stojko J, Kurek-Górecka A, Górecki M, Kabaładzik A, Kubina R, Moździerz A, Buszman E. Polyphenols from bee pollen: structure, absorption, metabolism and biological activity. Molecules. 2015 Dec;20(12):21732-49. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules201219800>
16. Arct J, Pytkowska K. Flavonoids as components of biologically active cosmeceuticals. Clinics in dermatology. 2008 Jul 1;26(4):347-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clindermatol.2008.01.004>
17. Panche AN, Diwan AD, Chandra SR. Flavonoids: an overview. Journal of nutritional science. 2016;5. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jns.2016.41>
18. Bonamigo T, Campos JF, Oliveira AS, Torquato HF, Balestieri JB, Cardoso CA, Paredes-Gamero EJ, de Picoli Souza K, Dos Santos EL. Antioxidant and cytotoxic activity of propolis of Plebeia droryana and Apis mellifera (Hymenoptera, Apidae) from the Brazilian Cerrado biome. PLoS One. 2017 Sep 12;12(9):e0183983. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0183983>

19. Bonamigo T, Campos JF, Alfredo TM, Balestieri JB, Cardoso CA, Paredes-Gamero EJ, de Picoli Souza K, Dos Santos EL. Antioxidant, cytotoxic, and toxic activities of propolis from two native bees in Brazil: *Scaptotrigona depilis* and *Melipona quadrifasciata anthidioides*. *Oxidative medicine and cellular longevity*. 2017 Mar 9;2017. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/1038153>
20. Bankova V. Chemical diversity of propolis and the problem of standardization. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*. 2005 Aug 22;100(1-2):114-7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2005.05.004>
21. Bittencourt ML, Ribeiro PR, Franco RL, Hilhorst HW, de Castro RD, Fernandez LG. Metabolite profiling, antioxidant and antibacterial activities of Brazilian propolis: Use of correlation and multivariate analyses to identify potential bioactive compounds. *Food Research International*. 2015 Oct 1;76:449-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2015.07.008>
22. Narimane S, Demircan E, Salah A, Salah R. Correlation between antioxidant activity and phenolic acids profile and content of Algerian propolis: Influence of solvent. *Pakistan journal of pharmaceutical sciences*. 2017 Jul 2;30.
23. Andrade JK, Denadai M, de Oliveira CS, Nunes ML, Narain N. Evaluation of bioactive compounds potential and antioxidant activity of brown, green and red propolis from Brazilian northeast region. *Food Research International*. 2017 Nov 1;101:129-38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2017.08.066>
24. Zhang C, Shen X, Chen J, Jiang X, Hu F. Identification of free radical scavengers from Brazilian green propolis using off-line HPLC-DPPH assay and LC-MS. *Journal of food science*. 2017 Jul;82(7):1602-7. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1750-3841.13730>
25. Socha R, Gałkowska D, Bugaj M, Juszcak L. Phenolic composition and antioxidant activity of propolis from various regions of Poland. *Natural Product Research*. 2015 Mar 4;29(5):416-22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786419.2014.949705>
26. Mujica V, Orrego R, Pérez J, Romero P, Ovalle P, Zúñiga-Hernández J, Arredondo M, Leiva E. The role of propolis in oxidative stress and lipid metabolism: a randomized controlled trial. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*. 2017 Apr 30;2017. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/4272940>
27. Jasprica I, Mornar A, Debeljak Ž, Smolčić-Bubalo A, Medić-Šarić M, Mayer L, Romić Ž, Bučan K, Balog T, Sobočanec S, Šverko V. In vivo study of propolis supplementation effects on antioxidant status and red blood cells. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. 2007 Apr 4;110(3):548-54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2006.10.023>
28. Fang Y, Li J, Ding M, Xu X, Zhang J, Jiao P, Han P, Wang J, Yao S. Ethanol extract of propolis protects endothelial cells from oxidized low-density lipoprotein-induced injury by inhibiting lectin-like oxidized low density lipoprotein receptor-1-mediated oxidative stress. *Experimental Biology and Medicine*. 2014 Dec;239(12):1678-87. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1535370214541911>
29. Sawamura T, Kume N, Aoyama T, Moriwaki H, Hoshikawa H, Aiba Y, Tanaka T, Miwa S, Katsura Y, Kita T, Masaki T. An endothelial receptor for oxidized low-density lipoprotein. *Nature*. 1997 Mar;386(6620):73-7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/386073a0>
30. Tian H, Sun HW, Zhang JJ, Zhang XW, Zhao L, Guo SD, Li YY, Jiao P, Wang H, Qin SC, Yao ST. Ethanol extract of propolis protects macrophages from oxidized low density lipoprotein-induced apoptosis by inhibiting CD36 expression and endoplasmic reticulum stress-C/EBP homologous protein pathway. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*. 2015 Dec;15(1):1-2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-015-0759-4>
31. Althanoon Z, Faisal IM, Ahmad AA, Merkhan MM, Merkhan MM. Pharmacological aspects of statins are relevant to their structural and physicochemical properties. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*. 2020;11(7):167-71. [ps://doi.org/10.31838/srp.2020.7.27](https://doi.org/10.31838/srp.2020.7.27)
32. Almkhtar HM, Faisal IM, Merkhan MM. Effects of statins on platelet count in hyperlipidemic patients. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2020 Apr;12(2):2640-4. <https://doi.org/10.31838/ijpr/2020.12.02.357>
33. Almkhtar HM, Faisal IM, Merkhan MM. Acute effect of atorvastatin in comparison with rosuvastatin on glucose homeostasis in hypercholesteremic patients. *Pharmacology*. 2021;25:25-34.
34. Younis HY, Imad A. Effect of zinc as an add on to metformin therapy on serum lipid profile and uric acid in type 2 diabetes mellitus patients. *Curr topics in Pharmacology*. 2021;25.
35. Almkhtar HM, Faisal IM, Merkhan MM. Short-term treatment with Atorvastatin selectively decreases Lymphocyte count. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*. 2022 Feb 26;15(2):689-94. <https://doi.org/10.52711/0974-360X.2022.00114>
36. Althanoon ZA, Merkhan MM. EFFECTS OF ZINC SUPPLEMENTATION ON METABOLIC STATUS IN PATIENTS WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME. *Acta Poloniae Pharmaceutica*. 2021;78(4) pp.521-6. <https://doi.org/10.32383/appdr/141348>
37. Zhao L, Pu L, Wei J, Li J, Wu J, Xin Z, Gao W, Guo C. Brazilian green propolis improves antioxidant function in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *International journal of environmental research and public health*. 2016 May;13(5):498. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph13050498>
38. Zambrano AM, Díaz CE, Zamora EE, Laverde AJ, Adame FT, Ronda JR, Quintanilla SB, Uvidia VC. Salud mental de los pacientes con enfermedades crónicas durante la pandemia por COVID-19. *Síndrome Cardiometabólico*. 2020;10(1):20-4.
39. Andrade AV, Cruz JG, Jiménez SI, Demera JA, Ronda JR, Uzhca BS, Tinoco YJ, Lara JC. Promoción de la actividad física en los pacientes con enfermedad cardiovascular durante el confinamiento por covid-19. *Síndrome Cardiometabólico*. 2020;10(1):16-9.

